

Interview Script

This document presents the script to conduct a semi-structured interview in the context of the study "A Preliminary Panoramic View of Continuous Software Engineering Adoption in Brazilian Organizations". The interviewee is a person (representing an organization) who participated in the study presented in (Santos Jr. et al, 2022).

Before the interview, the researcher must analyze data collected in the study reported in (Santos Jr. et al, 2022) and identify the stages, categories and CSE practices that stand out as the ones with highest and lowest adoption degrees in the organization.

Then, the researcher must conduct the interview aiming to better understand how CSE practices related to stages and categories with highest adoption degrees have been implemented in the organization and the reasons why certain CSE practices have been adopted in lower degrees or have not been adopted in the organization.

Questions to investigate CSE practices/stages/categories with highest adoption degrees:

To understand how the organization has performed practices related to StH stages /Eye of CSE categories with the highest adoption degrees:

- *How does your organization perform practices related to «Eye of CSE category or StH stage»?*

To go deeper into specific practices:

- *How has «CSE practice» been performed in your organization?*
- *Why has the practice been adopted?*
- *What artifacts does the practice generate?*
- *Which improvements were noticed when adopting the practice?*
- *Are there metrics to evaluate the practice?*
- *Are there plans to improve the practice?*
- *Do you want to comment anything else about practices/stages/categories that stand out in your organization?*

Questions to investigate CSE practices/stages/categories with lowest adoption degrees:

To understanding the reasons for or consequences of not performing some practices or adopting them to a low degree:

- *Why does your organization not perform some practices related to «Eye of CSE category or StH stage»?*

- Why does your organization not perform «CSE practice»?
- Have you tried to adopt the practice? Which problems have you faced?
- What impact has the non-adoption of the practice been on the development process and the business?
- Are there any plans to adopt it/them in the future?
- Do you want to comment anything else about practices/stages/categories that your organization has adopted at lowest degrees?

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